

Fabrication and Comprehensive Study of the Structural, Electrical, and Magnetic Properties of $MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$ Nano Ferrites Prepared via the Sol-Gel Auto-Combustion Technique

Bilal A. Omar

Department of Physics, College of Science,
University of Kirkuk, Kirkuk, Iraq

Rusul A. Najem

Aliraqia University, Iraq

Radhwan Ch. Mohsin

Department of Mechatronics and Robotics,
College of Control and System, University of Technology, Iraq

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ABSTRACT:

With the use of the sol-gel method and spontaneous combustion, a ferrite nano compound with the chemical formula ($MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$) for values of $X=0, 0.50, 1.00,$ and 1.50 has been prepared. It was then calcined for three hours at $850\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. EDX, XRD and FE-SEM were utilized for examining structural characteristics of the resultant ferrite. According to the findings, the ferrite has a spin-shaped crystal structure, a cubic phase, and grains that range in size from 24 to 42 nm. The electrical characteristics have been examined, and it has been discovered that dielectric constant value decreases as frequency increases, while alternating electrical conductivity value ($\sigma_{(a.c)}$) increases as frequency increases. Based on VSM, we discovered that $M_r \approx \pm 0.05$ emu/g, $M_s \approx 0.26$ emu/g, and $H_c \approx -250$ Oe.

Keywords: Nano-ferrites, Mg ions, sol -gel auto combustion approach, SEM, XRD, Magnetical properties.

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INTRODUCTION

There are many different methods to synthesize the spinel ferrites like solid-state reaction, Sol-gel, sol-gel auto combustion [1], and pulse laser deposition [2]. The spinel $MgFe_2O_4$ is a partially inverted spinel ferrite formed from plentiful elements (Mg, Fe, O) crystallized in a cubic system and has a variety of the technological applications [3,4]. In recent years, due to the possibility of controlling the nanostructure, high electrical resistance, desired morphology of spinal ferrites and high magnetic permeability [5,6]. These properties have been widely applied in many devices, such as magnetic resonance imaging, anode material for lithium-ion batteries, devices used in humidity sensing, drug delivery, recording, etc. [7]. The effect of Al^{+3} substitution on $MgFe_2O_4$ ferrite properties was

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examined in this study to give a precise understanding regarding the changes that occur due to the substitution, since spinel oxides exhibit flexibility due to their complex structures as well as the resulting high degrees of freedom [8].

METHODOLOGY

Materials and Synthesis

Sol-gel auto-combustion approach has been used in order to create nanoferrites with the chemical formula ($MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$), where $X=0, 0.50, 1.00,$ and 1.50 . The stored raw materials will be discussed later. Aluminum nitrate [$Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$], magnesium nitrate [$Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$], iron nitrate [$Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$], and citric acid [$C_6H_8O_7$] are the salts of materials employed in this study. They were utilized to make the $MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$ ferrite with $x = 0, 0.50, 1.00,$ and 1.50 . With the use of magnetic stirrers, metal nitrates and citric acid have been melted in deionized water and placed in a glass beaker to be collected at room temperature. For preparing the samples, the metal salts were weighed in precise weight ratios, mixed with deionized water, placed on a magnetic stirrer, and then progressively mixed with the ammonia solution to maintain a pH value of 7 through continuous cycles. To turn it into a gel, the reactants' temperature was progressively increased to $80^\circ C$. Next, we increased the reaction's temperature until it ignited by self-combustion, forming a fine powder. For three hours, the powder was roasted at $850^\circ C$. An agate mortar was used to grind the resultant powder, which was after that compressed into granules with the use of a dye with a diameter of 1.2 cm. Using a pressure of (7 tons) and keeping the samples under pressure for 3 minutes using a hydraulic press with a maximum load of 30 tons. Then it was sintered in an electric oven at a temperature $1200^\circ C$ for three hours and left to cool gradually.

Characterization

Miller coefficients, density, grain size, and atom size have been measured, and the results were compared with the analysis measurements with the use of the Image J program. XRD was used to study the structural properties regarding the ferrite compound utilizing radiation of the target material $CuK\alpha$ radiation with a wavelength of ($\lambda = 0.15406nm$) set as (20 mA), (40 kV), starting 2θ from (10° to 80°), and FE_SEM analysis methods, which confirmed the formation regarding the nano-compound. The magnetic characteristics of the prepared nano ferrites have been examined by VSM utilizing an application field up to 10k e, and the electrical properties have been investigated with the use of an LCR device, dielectric constant, and dielectric loss with a frequency range spanning from 50 Hz to 0.5 MHz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

XRD patterns of the $MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$ spinel ferrites for samples with ($x = 0, 0.50, 1,$ and 1.50) Fig 1 demonstrate that XRD patterns have a cubic phase and that the intensity of the peaks was varying as the Al ion concentration has increased. The reflection plane's (220), (002), (311), (400), (422), (511), and (440) can be attributed to the observed diffraction peaks. The results of the JCPDS (036-0398) and the XRD test agreed well [9].

The average crystallite size has been measured by Scherer's empirical relationship $\{D = 0.92 \lambda / [\beta \cos\theta]\}$ [10], where β is the maximum intensity XRD spectrum broadening, D : represents the average crystallite size, λ : denotes wavelength of XRD (Cu $k\alpha$ radiation, $0.15406nm$), θ : Bragg's angle.

The actual density of ($MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$) samples prepared by sol-gel method of spontaneous combustion of X-rays was determined using the equation $\{\rho_{x-ray} = (ZM_{wt} / N_a V)\}$ [11], where M_{wt} : denotes sample's molecular weight (Kg), a : denotes the lattice parameter by (\AA), N_a : denotes the Avogadro's number (Per mol).

The increase in the partial compensation of the Al^{+3} element can lead to a decrease in lattice constant (a) and also in the crystal size of samples with increasing Al^{+3} concentration.

Figure 1. Patterns of XRD for $(MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4)$ Samples

Table 1. Al^{+3} Partial Substitution Effects Onto Lattice Parameters, and X-Ray Density of $MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4$ Compound

Concentration of Al^{+3}	X = 0	X = 0.50	X 1.00	X 1.5
Lattice constant a (\AA^0)	8.3677	8.3180	8.2753	8.1869
$\rho_{x\text{-ray}}$ (g/cm^3)	5.316	5.307	5.281	5.073
Lattice volume V (\AA^0) ³	585.893	575.5151	566.6974	548.7294

We note from Figure 2 that the X-ray intensity decreases linearly with the Al^{+3} concentration as follows.

Figure 2. Relation of the $\rho_{x\text{-ray}}$ with an Increase of Concentration

EDAX

Figure 3 shows energy-dispersive X-ray (EDAX) spectra of magnesium ferrite samples substituted with aluminum. And summarizes the elemental composition obtained from the compound spectrum, showing the weight percentages of the detected elements. The analysis confirms the successful incorporation of the target elements into the synthesized material. The prominent peaks

corresponding to magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe), oxygen (O), and aluminum (Al) indicate the formation of a homogeneous ferrite structure, with no detectable impurities within the resolution of the EDAX technique.

Figure 3 EDAX Spectra of Magnesium Ferrite

Field Emission-Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM)

Is a highly advanced imaging method employed to analyze the surface morphology and microstructural features of materials with nanometer-scale precision. Owing to its finely focused and high-brightness electron beam[12]. According to the result from fig.4 It was observed that $(MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4)$ have diameters ranging between 24-42nm

Figure 4. FE-SEM Image of $(MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4)$ Nano Ferrite

Electrical properties

Electrical measurements of ferrites $(MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4)$ with partial substitution values of Al^{3+} ($X=0, 0.50, 1.00, 1.50$) include dielectric properties for ferrite, AC and DC conductivity.

Dielectric Characteristics

From Figure 5, we note that the dielectric constant changes with frequency. The higher the frequency, the lower the dielectric constant. The decline is faster in the low-frequency regions (100

Hz to 50 kHz) until it reaches a state of saturation in the high-frequency regions (50 kHz to 0.5 MHz). The dielectric constant was measured using the equation $\epsilon'_{f} = ct/\epsilon_0 A$ [13], $\epsilon_0 \approx (8.8540 \times 10^{-14} F/cm)$. The dielectric constant value is larger at lower frequency values due to grain boundaries, defects, oxygen vacancies, and diffusion of Fe²⁺ ions. [13]

Figure 5. The Real Part of Dielectric Constant's for $(MgAl_xFe_{2-x}O_4)$ at a Variable Value of x

A.C. Conductivity

The prepared compound's alternating conductivity ($\sigma_{a.c}$) was measured within the frequency range of (50Hz – 0.5 MHz) at room temperature. For the prepared ferrite models, Figure 6 shows the change in conductivity as function of the applied electric field frequency. The findings demonstrated that as the frequency of applied electric field increases, the alternating conductivity rises linearly. Either the polarization of the dipoles or the distribution of ions inside the crystal lattice—that is, the rotation of the dipoles, or the automatic alignment of the dipoles between two equal equilibrium sites—are responsible for the variation in the conductivity value [14,15].

Figure 6. Variation of σ_{ac} with Frequency

Magnetic Properties

VSM studies

The VSM system is utilized for measuring the magnetic characteristics of the materials as a function

of the temperature, time, and magnetic field [18]. A sample magnetometer (VSM) is the most common measurement method for identifying a hysteretic ring. The magnetic behavior of the compound was examined using a magnetometer of the vibrational sample at room temperature, located at Kashan University, as shown in Fig 7:

Figure 7. Hysteric Loop for $(\text{MgAl}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{O}_4)$ Nano Ferrite

We used an application field up to 10k e. From the magnetic hysteria ring, the parameters were estimated as follows: $M_r \approx \pm 0.05$ emu/g, $M_s \approx 0.26$ emu/g, $H_c \approx \pm 250$ Oe. We observe a narrow and semi-linear shape, which indicates the soft magnetic behavior of the ferrite compound as well as weak ferromagnetic features. These values indicate that the material can be magnetized and demagnetized, which is a desirable property in soft magnetic materials. Low coercion and residual magnetization indicate minimal energy loss during the magnetic cycle, making this material a potential candidate for use in magnetic sensing, switching, and electromagnetic shielding [16,17].

CONCLUSION

Sol-Gel method was successfully used to create polycrystalline magnesium ferrite ($\text{MgAl}_x\text{Fe}_{2-x}$) with a substitution ratio of ($x = 0$ to 1.5) utilizing (Mg, Al, Fe) nitrates. Its magnetic, structural, and electrical characteristics were examined. Ferrite nanostructure formation is revealed by the XRD pattern. The Scherer equation was used for measuring the particle size, which falls between 24 and 42 nm. Fine particles with some agglomerations are visible in the FE-SEM image. EDX measurements verified that the ferrite samples contained the components Mg, Fe, Al, and O. The dielectric constant varies with frequency, exhibiting normal dielectric dispersion at low frequencies and remaining almost constant at high frequencies. The particles are super paramagnetic if the AC conductivity increases linearly with frequency. The low values of saturation magnetism and coercivity exhibit mono domain behavior. All the above results indicate that the sol-gel spontaneous combustion method is an effective method for producing ultrafine magnesium ferrite particles with exceptional electrical and magnetic properties.

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